

Frequently used acronyms:

AAP: Ambient Air Pollution

IHD: Ischemic Heart Disease

ACM: All-Cause Mortality

COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

LC: Lung Cancer

ALRI: Acute Lower Respiratory Infection

LD: Lockdown

LD1: Lockdown 1 (25 Mar - 31 May 2020)

LD2: Lockdown 2 (05 Apr - 15 Jun 2021)

NCAP: National Clean Air Programme (Through Indian Government)

NAAQS: Indian National Ambient Air Quality Standards

PM: Particulate Matter

AQG: Air Quality Guidelines

RR Relative Risk

IT: Interim Target